

THE USE OF THERMOMINERAL WATERS IN OBTAINING A THIRD-GENERATION BIOFUEL

M.M.Axmatqulov

Institutes of hydrogeology and engineering geology

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Annotation: In this article, the whole world is now switching to green energy to solve one of the most pressing environmental problems today. In order to implement these works, instead of oil and gas and coal products, renewable electricity is being gradually switched over. One of these energies is a third-generation biofuel, and the issue of obtaining them using thermo-mineral waters has been raised.

Keywords; Third generation biofuel, Thermomineral waters, warm climate, ecological problems, transition to green energy, economic growth.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Xozirgi kunda dolzarp muammolardan biri bolayotgan ekalogik muammolarni xal etish uchun hozirda butun jaxon yashil inergiyaga o'tmoqda. Bu ishlarni amalga oshirish uchun nef- gaz va ko'mir maxsulotlarining o'rniga qayta tiklanuvchan elektir inergiyalarga bosqichma bosqich o'tilmoqda. Bu energiyalardan bir uchinchi avlod bioyoqilg'isi bolib ularni termo mineral suvlar yordamida olish masalasi qo'yilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Uchinchi avlod bioyoqilo'isi, Termomineral suvlar, issiq iqlim, ekalogik muammolar, Yashil inergiyaga o'tish, Iqtisodiy qo'tarilish.

Аннотация: В этой статье весь мир сейчас переходит на зеленую энергетику, чтобы решить одну из самых актуальных сегодня экологических проблем. Для реализации этих работ вместо нефтегазовой и угольной продукции постепенно осуществляется переход на возобновляемую электроэнергию. Одной из таких энергий является биотопливо третьего поколения, и поднят вопрос его получения с использованием термоминеральных вод.

Ключевые слова; Биотопливо третьего поколения, Термоминеральные воды, теплый климат, экологические проблемы, переход на зеленую энергетику, экономический рост.

Introduction; A complete study of the composition of underground thermomineral waters of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the economic development of their effective use is one of the important issues today.

Nowadays, as a result of the rapid increase in the human population, there are problems of electricity, heat energy and fuel. In order to solve such problems, the transition to third-generation bio-fuels can be a solution to solve these problems at the present time. The use of third-generation biofertilizers also helps to prevent environmental and climate changes, which are becoming a global problem today.

The main part; Growing concerns about global climate change, energy security, high oil prices, and dwindling oil reserves have spurred the shift to biofuels as a viable and renewable alternative to fossil fuels. Given the current state of biofuel production technology, this paper will help address why current measures for biofuel production, consumption and trade are still insufficient to reduce greenhouse gas emissions to the extent necessary to combat climate change and achieve sustainability.

The paper discusses in depth the various challenges and limitations associated with the current state of biofuels and highlights the importance of transitioning to next-generation biofuels, which promise to demonstrate much greater potential to combat economic, social, and environmental challenges. The third generation biofuel is considered to be a fuel obtained from algae. 1978-yildan 1996-yilgacha AKSH Energy Department Suva turlari guidance of Associate Professor Up egli checked the yesuns. A study conducted in California, Hawaii and New Mexico showed that some industries are currently studying MOS degan. The 6th floor has an area of 1000 m² with a yetishtirili swimming pool. The New Mexicadaga Marine CO₂ basin is landlocked. The yield is 50 hectares. The area is 1 m² ha. The area is 200 thousand hectares. The area is 5% of automobile consumption. At least 200 thousand hectares of land occupied by Jews are spent on the purchase of weapons for 0.1% less Tribute. Technology solves both sides of the puzzle.

The 1990s saw the end of low-cost oil production technologies thanks to the ishlab chikarishiga kirmadi industry[1]. There is a strong demand to replace fossil fuels that cause pollution and global warming from non-renewable sources. In this context, microalgae are considered a promising source of biofuels, among other valuable products, because they do not need agricultural land, can increase their biomass eightfold in 1 day and accumulate more triglycerides than terrestrial oil crops.

Due to the lack of large-scale production capacity for all the new technologies currently involved in algal biofuel production, cost-benefit analysis is limited by several considerations and assumptions. For each different study, the parameters vary from the selection of the algal strain to the final production, so changes in production costs can be measured using sensitivity analysis. [2].

Summary. Taking into account the above, it should be noted that one of the urgent tasks of today in our republic is the use of underground thermomineral water as an alternative source of energy (in place of gas and coal) along with the production of third-generation biofuels in order to develop entrepreneurship in the regions. Despite the fact that underground thermomineral water resources, which are of great importance in the national economy and restoration of human health, are limited, we will use them effectively. In some regions, the thermal mineral water coming out of the ground contains saline salts. If the extracted water is not used carefully, it can cause salinization of the soil and the loss of green areas and various plants in the environment.

In order to eliminate such problems, installation of devices (cranes) that control the water coming out under pressure, controlling the use of underground water for the right purposes and rationally will lead to an increase in the economic and export potential of our independent Uzbekistan, the creation of new jobs, an increase in the income of the population, and an improvement in the standard of living will come.

Literatur

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